

Minimalist Painting as a Therapeutic Remedy to Individuals with Mental Health Challenges in Imo State, Nigeria

Chidimma Cindy Ogonnaya, Nwankwo, PhD

Department of Fine Art, Faculty of Environmental Design, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria,
Kaduna State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study aims to investigate minimalist painting as a therapeutic remedy to individuals with mental health challenges in Imo State, Nigeria. Painting boosts memory recollection skills and works to sharpen the mind through conceptual visualization and implementation. People who frequently use creative outlets such as writing, painting, and drawing have less chance of developing memory loss illnesses, like dementia and Alzheimer's, as they age. The creation or appreciation of art is used to help people explore emotions, develop self-awareness, cope with stress, boost self-esteem, and work on social skills. Minimalist art focuses on things like geometry, line, and color. Early works tended to be monochromatic, limited to one color and related hues (like black, grey, and white). Another way to identify a Minimalist painting is by looking for hard-edged, precise borders between areas of color. Created in the United States in the 1960's. Minimalism art is an extreme type of abstract art that usually is depicted through simplistic shapes and hard edges, all while exposing the essence of the forms and materials used. The movement challenged preconceived notions of what art is and could be. Painting allows for emotional release because it stimulates the creative side of the mind while focusing on the attention in one place, which can lower anxiety. In this way, the creative outlet improves mental health significantly. In particular, painters exercise the parts of their brain responsible for memory and concentration. It also provides an opportunity for people to learn and find meaning or inspiration in their lives. "Various studies have shown that viewing art can heighten mood, reduce anxiety and stress, and increase the overall sense of wellness and contentment. Art possesses the ability to boost one's confidence and facilitate a journey of self-discovery. Engaging in art helps individuals explore their inner thoughts and feelings, leading to a deeper understanding of the self and enhanced self-esteem. Art therapy is used to reduce conflicts and distress, improve cognitive functions, foster self-esteem, and build emotional resilience and social skills. It engages the mind, body, and spirit in ways that are distinct from verbal communication.

Keywords: Minimalist, Painting, Therapeutic, Remedy, Individuals, Mental, Health, Challenges.

INTRODUCTION

There have been several minimalist painters over the years with the most prominent being Ellsworth Kelly. He used blocks of color with defined hard edges to create numerous minimalist art pieces. Frank Stella became famous for his series of Black Paintings which he created freehand using a house painters brush to craft identical sets of black stripes. Donald Judd wrote an essay called Specific Objects in which he introduced the idea that art could be free from emotion and can be everyday items. Minimalist art has had its effect on society today through music, graphic design, interior design, and architecture. Some people now are even living in a simplistic nature by only having the necessities of life. (Aikins, & Akoi-Jackson, 2020).

Minimalism was an art movement that developed in the United States in the late 1950s and that reached its peak in the mid to late 1960s. It is also called Minimalist Art or ABC art, because it focuses on basic elements. It grew out of the ideas expressed in the early 20th century by people like the Russian artist Kazimir Malevich, who pioneered Abstract Art by painting non-representational pictures without a reference to the landscapes, people, and still-life scenes found in the real world. Minimalism was also a reaction to the most prominent style of art pursued in the 1950s, abstract expressionism, in which the art conveyed multiple meanings of intense emotions and ideas, sometimes created in spontaneous or unplanned ways. Abstract Expressionists often used thick brushstrokes that were clearly done by hand. An example of Abstract Expressionism is Willem de Kooning's work Woman V, done in the early 1950s. It is aggressive, emotional, and almost violent in its brushstrokes and lines. (Blomdahl, Rusner, & Björklund 2016).

Mental disorders constitute a huge social and economic burden for health care systems worldwide (Zschucke et al., 2013; Kenbubpha et al., 2018). In China, the lifetime prevalence of mental disorders was 24.20%, and 1-month prevalence of mental disorders was 14.27% (Xu et al., 2017). The situation is more severely in other countries, especially for developing ones like Nigeria. Given the large numbers of people in need and the humanitarian imperative to reduce suffering, there is an urgent need to implement scalable mental health interventions to address this burden. While pharmacological treatment is the first choice for mental disorders to alleviate the major symptoms, many antipsychotics contribute to poor quality of life and debilitating adverse effects. Therefore, clinicians have turned toward to complementary treatments, such as art therapy in addressing the health needs of patients more than half a century ago.

Art therapy, is defined by the British Association of Art Therapists as: “a form of psychotherapy that uses art media as its primary mode of expression and communication. Clients referred to art therapists are not required to have experience or skills in the arts. The art therapist’s primary concern is not to make an esthetic or diagnostic assessment of the client’s image. The overall goal of its practitioners is to enable clients to change and grow on a personal level through the use of artistic materials in a safe and convenient environment” (British Association of Art Therapists, 2015), whereas as: “an integrative mental health and human services profession that enriches the lives of individuals, families, and communities through active art-making, creative process, applied psychological theory, and human experience within a psycho-therapeutic relationship” (American Art Therapy Association, 2018) according to the American Art Association. It has

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gradually become a well-known form of spiritual support and complementary therapy (Faller and Schmidt, 2004; Nainis et al., 2006). During the therapy, art therapists can utilize many different art materials as media (i.e., visual art, painting, drawing, music, dance, drama, and writing) (Deshmukh et al., 2018; Chiang et al., 2019). Among them, drawings and paintings have been historically recognized as the most useful part of therapeutic processes within psychiatric and psychological specialties (British Association of Art Therapists, 2015). Moreover, many other art forms gradually fall under the prevue of their own professions (e.g., music therapy, dance/movement therapy, and drama therapy) (Deshmukh et al., 2018). Thus, these studies only focused on studies of art therapy which mainly includes painting and drawing as media.

Burton, (2009), specifically, focuses on capturing psychodynamic processes by means of “inner pictures,” which become visible by the creative process (Steinbauer et al., 1999). These pictures reflect the psychopathology of different psychiatric disorders and even their corresponding therapeutic process based on specific rules and criterion (Steinbauer & Taucher, 2001). It has been gradually recognized and used as an alternative treatment for therapeutic processes within psychiatric and psychological specialties, as well as medical and neurology-based scientific audiences.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The review of literature in this article adopts the method of "systematic literature review integrated process". This process involves an independent literature review, aiming to establish the foundational theories during the early stages of research by comprehending existing literature on the minimalist painting as a therapeutic remedy to individuals with mental health challenges in Imo State, Nigeria. The development of art therapy comes partly from the artistic expression of the belief in unspoken things, and partly from the clinical work of art therapists in the medical setting with various groups of patients (Malchiodi, 2013). It is defined as the application of artistic expressions and images to individuals who are physically ill, undergoing invasive medical procedures, such as surgery or chemotherapy for clinical usage (Bar-Sela et al., 2007; Forzoni et al., 2010; Liebmann and Weston, 2015). The American Art Therapy Association describes its main functions as improving cognitive and sensorimotor functions, fostering self-esteem and self-awareness, cultivating emotional resilience, promoting insight, enhancing social skills, reducing and resolving conflicts and distress, and promoting societal and ecological changes (American Art Therapy Association, 2018).

Therefore, this review aims to explore its clinical applications and future perspectives to summary its global pictures, so as to provide more clinical treatment options and research directions for therapists and researchers.

Willem de Kooning, Woman V, 1952-1953

By the late 1950s, some artists began rebelling against what they considered Abstract Expressionism's excesses. They headed in a completely opposite direction toward Minimalist Art.

Several important characteristics identify Minimalist Art. One of the most common is repetition, or creating multiple images of the same shape, especially simple geometric forms like lines and squares. Artists repeat shapes and produce paintings composed of vertical color blocks. Many works are extremely simple, pared down to the fewest possible lines or forms needed to paint the image. Areas are smooth and finished, devoid of obvious brushstrokes or hint of the artist's hand. Minimalist art focuses on things like geometry, line, and color. Early works tended to be monochromatic, limited to one color and related hues (like black, grey, and white). Another way to identify a Minimalist painting is by looking for hard-edged, precise borders between areas of color. There is no shading or subtle transition. (Dobber, Latour, Scholte, Barkhof, et al .2018).

Minimalist Painters

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Some of the most prominent Minimalist artists were sculptors, people like Sol LeWitt and Donald Judd. The latter began his art career as a painter and art critic in the 1940s. His work is important because it helped to define minimalism, especially his essay "Specific Objects", which advocated for art made from everyday materials. Judd eventually transitioned into woodcuts and then focused the rest of his career on sculpture. Among prominent Minimalist painters, one of the earliest was Ellsworth Kelly (1923 - 2015), whose works featured hard-edged precise borders between blocks of color. First active in the mid-1950s, he predates the clear establishment of Minimalism, but in paintings like *Red Yellow Blue White and Black* from 1953, he clearly displays the characteristics later connected to Minimalist Art, especially hard-edged flat areas of color. He later moved on to more sculptural works. (Dzokoto, Anum, Affram, Agbavitoh, Dadzie, et al. 2021).

Ellsworth Kelly, *Red Yellow Blue White and Black*, 1953

One of the most important Minimalist painters is Frank Stella. In the late 1950s, he caught the immediate attention of the art world with his series of *Black Paintings*: monochromatic paintings with uniform geometric lines created in bands of black paint. An example of one of these works is *The Marriage of Reason and Squalor II*, painted in 1959. When asked to define Minimalist Art, Stella summed it up this way: "What you see is what you get." (Garcia, Martinez et. al. 2016)

Frank Stella, *The Marriage of Reason and Squalor II*, 1959

In his later work, Stella moved away from monochromatic palettes and instead shifted to flat areas of bright color. An example is this work, *Hagamatana II* from 1967, which still possesses the geometric and repetitive shapes and hard-edged borders of Minimalism. (Dzokoto, et al. 2021).

Frank Stella, Hagamatana II, 1967

Minimalism had its peak in the late 1960s and was eventually eclipsed by other art movements. During its heyday, critics were not always favorable to Minimalism's restrained cool style, with one critic deriding the works as novelties that lessened the impact of paintings as works of art. But Minimalism proved to be of enduring influence. Look around today in design, fine art, and interior decoration and you will still see the bold areas of color, hard-edged lines, and other elements that it popularized. (Guest, Namey, & Chen, 2020).

Art therapy is a field grounded in research-based science that combines active art-making, the creative process, applied psychological theory, and the human experience within a psychotherapeutic relationship. Art therapy, as a non-pharmacological medical complementary and alternative therapy, has been used as one of medical interventions with good clinical effects on mental disorders. (Garcia, Martinez-Cengotitabengoa, Lopez-Zurbano et. al. (2016)

As defined by the British Association of Art Therapists, art therapy is a form of psychotherapy that uses art media as its primary mode of communication. Based on above literature, several highlights need to be summarized. The main media of art therapy include painting, drawing, music, drama, dance, drama, and writing (Chiang et al., 2019). Main contents of painting and drawing include blind drawing, spiral drawing, drawing moods and self-portraits (Legrand et al., 2017; Abbing et al., 2018; Papangelo et al., 2020). Art therapy is mainly used for cancer, depression and anxiety, autism, dementia and cognitive impairment, as these patients are reluctant to express themselves in words (Attard & Larkin, 2016; Deshmukh et al., 2018; Chiang et al., 2019). It plays an important role in facilitating engagement when direct verbal interaction becomes

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difficult, and provides a safe and indirect way to connect oneself with others (Papangelo et al., 2020). Moreover, we found that art therapy has been gradually and successfully used for patients with mental disorders with positive outcomes, mainly reducing suffering from mental symptoms. These findings suggest that art therapy can not only be served as a useful therapeutic method to assist patients to open up and share their feelings, views, and experiences, but also as an auxiliary treatment for diagnosing diseases to help medical specialists obtain complementary information different from conventional tests. (Koomson, Osei, & Essel, 2021).

Brain and Health Benefits of Painting

Raffaelli, (2022), found that Keeping mind and body sharp is important throughout the entire lives, but it becomes even more important as aged. While staying physically fit is important for good health, finding a creative outlet keeps mind strong while also expanding horizons. Painting provides a fun, new hobby that sharpens mind and delivers numerous health benefits. Great benefits of painting that promote mental health and improve overall quality of life. (Hu, Lu, Huang & Zang, 2021).

Painting Develops Creativity

This may sound obvious enough, but what might not be obvious is that painting stimulates both the right and left sides of the brain. In painting, we use the left side of the brain to tackle rational, logical challenges. How to structure the painting, for example, while the left side of the brain is used for more creative challenges, helping the painter visualise their work before they even set up their easel. Painting is an all-brain exercise, strengthening the mind and triggering dopamine activity in the brain. So spending time indulging creative spirit is basically aerobics for the brain, Painting supports emotional wellbeing. A picture says a thousand words, and painting can be a hugely cathartic experience, allowing to access feelings buried deep within the subconscious. (Ndaa, Kwakye, & Shann, 2021).

Painting can also help deal with those feelings by giving them a physical shape, removing the anguish involved when keeping feelings hidden. This is why psychologists often prescribe art therapy for patients who have suffered psychological trauma. It helps to release emotions in a safe, non-threatening environment. By learning to better express self. Through the medium of art, painting can be an act of self-care that supports emotional well-being. (Koomson, Osei & Essel 2021).

Painting Builds Problem-Solving and Motor Skills

Osei, (2021), found that a lot of people think that painting only improves creative skills, but many would be surprised to know that it promotes critical thinking, too. An artist must think conceptually to bring multiple solutions to life while painting. What the artist imagines when beginning a painting often changes drastically during the painting process, due to color limitations or unexpected outcomes that occur during artistic implementation. The artistic vision evolves during the painting process, building important problem-solving skills. Thinking outside the box becomes second nature to a painter. Motor skills also improve when a person picks up painting as a hobby. Dexterously handling a paintbrush increases mobility in the hands and fingers. The fine motor skills that a painter develops eventually become mental shortcuts that the brain implements in everyday life. (Read, Jilka, & Singh, 2023).

Sometimes paintings rarely turn out as originally planned. Although this can be frustrating and disappointing, it turns out that this can actually be good. Unexpected results have two benefits, for starters quickly learn to deal with disappointment, and in time (often through repeated error) to realise that when one door closes, another opens. You quickly learn to adapt and come up with creative solutions to the problems the painting presents, and this means that thinking outside the box becomes second nature to the painter. Creative problem-solving skills are incredibly useful in daily life and mean more likely to be able to quickly come up with a solution when a problem arises. Robinson, (Sulz, Gleddie, & Berg, 2021).

Painting Improves Memory and Concentration

Painting boosts memory recollection skills and works to sharpen the mind through conceptual visualization and implementation. People who frequently use creative outlets such as writing, painting, and drawing have less chance of developing memory loss illnesses, like dementia and Alzheimer's, as they age. Painting also allows individuals a chance to express their feelings and emotions without words. It can be tough opening up sometimes, so painting is a great way to

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release inner thoughts. Individuals that paint use art to overcome shyness and convey their personality. (Sipsma Ofori-Atta, Canavan, Osei-Akoto, Udry & Bradley, 2018).

Brain is essentially working out when painting, which means that painting boosts memory function and sharpens the mind. In particular, painters exercise the parts of their brain responsible for memory and concentration. So not only is painting hobby sparking joy and makes better feelings, but it also takes care of health and safeguards brain functions for the future. (Stroup &, Gray, 2018).

Painting Develops Communication Skills

Art therapy can be practiced individually or in group settings. In the group context, it offers individuals an opportunity to connect with others who may be facing similar challenges. Engaging in artistic activities together can foster a sense of belonging and mutual support, reducing feelings of isolation. Additionally, art therapy can act as a conduit for non-verbal communication, enabling individuals to express themselves in a safe and inclusive environment. Painting helps to tap into subconscious and allows to communicate feelings of yourself to the outside world through the pieces created. Not only this, but it also, in simple terms, acts as an ice-breaker, giving a shared interest with thousands of other artists and art appreciators around the world. (Weobong,-Ngibise, Sakyi, & Lund. 2023).

Art therapy provides a safe and supportive environment for individuals to express themselves freely. Through the creative process, suppressed emotions, trauma, or unconscious thoughts can be unveiled, allowing individuals to confront and process them in a controlled manner. This release of pent-up emotions can be cathartic and have a positive impact on an individual's mental well-being, leading to a greater sense of emotional balance and resilience. (Zhang, Hu, Yu, & Xu, 2021).

Painting Provides Stress Relief

The creative process itself can have a calming and meditative effect, promoting relaxation and reducing stress levels. Art therapy provides an outlet for managing stress and anxiety by redirecting focus onto the creative process. Through art, individuals can learn healthy coping mechanisms and develop problem-solving skills that can be utilized in their daily lives. This can significantly reduce the negative impact of mental health issues on their overall well-being. (Weobong,-Ngibise, Sakyi, & Lund. 2023).

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Stress is a problem everyone deals with to some degree during all stages of life. High levels of stress and anxiety contribute to mental health issues. Painting and other artistic pursuits offer an emotional release or outlet for people that struggle with stress or are having a stressful moment in their lives. Focusing on painting allows person's mind to relax and let go of all the problems and demands that may have led to stress. When people create something beautiful through painting, they stimulate the creative mind while also relieving mental strain. Releasing anxiety in the form of painting helps a person unwind and let go of all the pressures that plague the mind. It is not surprise that low-stress levels lead to a happier, healthier lifestyle and helps improve overall mental health, (Zhang, Hu, Yu, & Xu, 2021).

Painters enter a world of their own as they create, and this allows them albeit unconsciously to separate themselves from the stresses and strains of everyday life. No mortgage, no office politics just colour and shade, instead. Painting allows to escape daily struggles, and it lifts up mind and soul. By focusing on painting, we achieve what art critic and philosopher, Arthur Danto, calls "transfiguration of the commonplace," as painting becomes imbued with meanings that go well beyond their literal worth. In other words, painting may not turn out like you thought it would, but somehow just by contemplating it, and studying it, you feel lifted by its beauty. (Van Westrhenen, Fritz, Vermeer, Boelen, & Kleberg 2019).

Building Self-Esteem and Empowerment:

Art therapy emphasizes the process rather than the final product, removing the pressure of creating something aesthetically pleasing. This approach fosters self-acceptance and boosts self-esteem, as individuals learn to value and appreciate their unique creative expression. By building confidence in their own abilities, individuals can experience a newfound sense of empowerment, positively impacting their mental health and overall quality of life. (Weobong, Sakyi, & Lund, 2023). Creating beautiful work through painting encourages a more optimistic approach to life. A painter starts by setting goals to advance their painting skills and become a more experienced artist. When a person reaches the next skill level, their achievement inspires a positive emotional reaction. Over time, a painter's progress and skills deter negative emotions and provide pleasure and happiness for the individual. Painting boosts self-esteem and inspires people to reach new levels of skill. Painting also produces a relaxing, open environment where artists feel safe to explore their own creativity. The reward of growing and expanding artistic skills creates a sense of accomplishment. Creating visually appealing artwork that others admire gives the painter a sense of pride and happiness in the work. (Zhang, Hu, Yu, & Xu, 2021).

Engaging in art-making often involves making choices, reflecting on the process, and exploring the visual outcomes. This encourages individuals to examine their creative choices, symbols, and metaphors used in their artwork, offering valuable insights into their subconscious mind. Art therapy enables individuals to gain a deeper understanding of their emotions, thoughts, and patterns of behavior, aiding in personal growth and self-awareness. Weobong, Ae-Ngibise, Sakyi, & Lund, (2023).

Painting Nurtures Emotional Growth

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Artists pour out their emotions through the process of painting. This practice encourages individuals to look at their own emotional state and take stock of emotions they may not even realize they have. Releasing emotions through artwork is a cathartic experience for many people, at all ages. In fact, many therapists suggest painting or drawing as a treatment for patients who have suffered psychologically painful encounters. Letting out emotions by painting promotes healing through abstract emotional expression. Those who paint experience an increase in their emotional intelligence level. Allowing your emotions to come out in painting helps you understand your own emotional state and realize what contributes to your varying moods and stress levels. (Oppong, Kretchy, Imbeah, & Afrane, 2016).

Srivastava, (2009), opined that playing around with different painting types can help understand what triggers certain feelings such as happiness, sadness, love, or anger. Often, the emotions you feel while creating this work can project onto the people that view your paintings. Painters have the ability to bring others happiness, sharing their positive mindset with viewers. This skill makes painter's better company for themselves and those around them. While painting might not contribute much physical fitness, the cognitive benefits to overall health are incredibly valuable. Given all the beneficial attributes to this artistic hobby, it is clear that painting builds strong mental health in individuals of every age. Taking up painting promotes a happy mood not only in the artist but also in people around them. By engaging in various art forms such as painting, drawing, sculpting, or collage-making, individuals can explore their inner world, gain insights, and develop coping mechanisms to manage their mental health challenges. (Read, Jilka, & Singh, 2023).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Read, Jilka, & Singh (2023), systematically reviewed in detail in clinical situation on PubMed for art therapy in an attempt to explore its theoretical basis, clinical applications, future perspectives, and summary to its global pictures. Since drawings and paintings have been historically recognized as a useful part of therapeutic processes in art therapy, focused on studies of art therapy which mainly includes painting and drawing to media. As a result, a total of 413 literature were identified. After carefully reading full articles, they found that art therapy has been gradually and successfully used for patients with mental disorders with positive outcomes, mainly reducing suffering from mental symptoms, (Van Westrhenen, Fritz, Vermeer, Boelen, & Kleber 2019). These disorders mainly include depression disorders and anxiety, cognitive impairment and dementias, Alzheimer's disease, schizophrenia, and autism. These findings suggest that art therapy can not only be served as a useful therapeutic method to assist patients to open up and share their feelings, views, and experiences, but also as an auxiliary treatment for diagnosing diseases to help medical specialists obtain complementary information different from conventional tests. They found that art therapy has great potential in clinical applications on mental disorders to be further explored. (Willyard, Crothers, Schmitt, & Hughes. Et al. 2022).

Hu Y. et al. (2021), recommended art therapy as one of the non-pharmacological interventions for treating CMHDs. According to the American Art Therapy Association (2021), art therapy integrates mental health and human services by using active art making, creative process, applied

psychological theory, and human experience which are suitable for people of all ages. Some examples of art therapy include drawing, painting, dance, music, ceramics and etc. Raffaelli (2012), included that drawing is one of the approaches that is popular with and widely used by the art therapy community. One of the main goals of art therapy is to improve people's well-being and functioning capabilities. There has been reports on the effectiveness of art therapy in some context.

Robinson et al. (2021) also suggested that art therapy is not just essential for children but adults can also reap a lot of health benefits throughout life. According to UK professionals in the field of art therapy, the key benefits of art therapy were the clients' ability to express themselves verbally and artistically, providing evidence to suggest that therapists were confident and cognizant with art therapy. Westrhenen et al. (2019) also determined whether the use of creative arts in a group psychotherapy program for kids might impact their post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms, behavioural issues, and post-traumatic growth (PTG). The authors reported that art therapy was helpful to re-establish or build appropriate emotion regulation after experiencing extreme stress by decreasing hyperarousal symptoms. The study added that South Africa is the first and only country in the African continent to offer art therapy as a course in their degree program at the University of Johannesburg (Van Westrhenen, Fritz, Vermeer, Boelen, & Kleber, 2019).

Sipsma, Ofori et al (2023) found that in Ghana, mental health disorders are a leading cause of years lived with disability. About 13% of the adult population is estimated to be affected by mental health disorders of varying forms and may require either pharmacological or non-pharmacological care According to Kpobi and Swartz (2019), mental health treatment in Ghana involves a combination of biomedical, indigenous and faith-healing approaches. Even though 20% of patients had sought help from alternative healers for the first episode of illness, the majority of patients sought help from biomedical facilities despite the assumed supernatural illness beliefs. Medical pluralism comes with its own challenges such as mutual distrust, power differentials, conceptual and methodological problems, and a lack of organizational support and resources (Read, Jilka & Singh, 2023).

Ursula et al. (2023), suggest that community engagement, dialogue, and mutual learning may enable more effective and sustainable collaboration between ethno medicine and biomedicine (Read, Jilka & Singh, 2023). The Ghana Health Service provides mental health care through psychiatrists and clinical psychologists. The perceived high cost of biomedical services is one key factor that affects the treatment (Kpobi & Swart 2019). Ghana is a country where art thrives (Aikins, & Akoi-Jackson, 2020). With a strong history of traditional modern art types, art has also been a part of Ghanaian culture. For example, through kente weaving, beads making, adinkra symbols, textiles, music, ceramics, basket weaving and theatrical plays among others. Ghana has several art galleries that exhibits paintings and sculptures to the public at the regional and community levels. Some of these art galleries include Arts Alliance Ghana Limited, Wild Geeko, Nubuke Foundation, the Aburi Craft Center, Loom and Endrose African Art Gallery. Ghana is also known for the Chalewote festival, a street art festival that celebrates the rich art culture of Ghana (Seli & Baisie 2023).

Willyard & Men (2022), assessed the knowledge and the use of art therapy amongst clinical psychologists in treating people with mental disorders. This section discusses the major themes identified in the study by comparing the findings to other studies in different contexts. The majority of the participants were females although an almost equal number to males. It is a wide held stereotype that psychologists are mostly female, however the trend is changing. Females are more drawn to psychology because they perceive themselves as more empathic than men (Willyard & Men 2022). A study done by Crothers et al. (2010) showed the factors related to gender-based differences include a greater likelihood that women tend to take time off to have or care for children, take family leave or work part-time, and work in non-profit or local government sectors compared to males. With these findings, many women are drawn to the flexibility that a career in psychology provides (Crothers, Schmitt, Hughes, Lipinski, Theodore, Radliff, et. 2010).

METHODOLOGY

This research is mainly based on Minimalist painting a study on therapeutic remedy to individuals with mental health challenges in Imo state, Nigeria. The questionnaire survey in this study is designed on the basis of the knowledge, skills, and key points of painting creation. The questionnaire survey is mainly to test the cognitive situation of individuals using painting materials in painting practice. At the same time, the differences in the usage and cognition of painting materials by individuals of different genders and ages were analyzed through research data.

Minimalist. Findings showed that painting can provide inspiration and creativity for artists. At the same time, painting provides new sources of inspiration for artistic works (Okada & Ishibashi, 2017). The study analyzed the artistic features of minimalist painting from four aspects: point, line, surface, and color, and found that a strong ability to summarize, imagine, and create can be achieved based on these, while also combining with other elements of other art forms, such as modeling, color application, composition, and expression. This study believes that minimalist painting is a therapeutic remedy to individual with mental health challenges not only provides artistic experiences but also relieves individuals with mental stress, inspires artists, and stimulates subjective happiness through visual image. (Stroup, & Gray, 2018).

In addition, specific visual features such as simplified and independent shapes, bold color contrasts, high purity, freedom and emphasis on subject composition can enhance the visual appeal and artistic value of individual artwork as important. The study suggests that analyzing the cognitive and visual characteristics of minimalistic painting can inspire artists to create more creative and alluring works of art, thereby enhancing the audience's artistic enjoyment. (Weobong, Ae-Ngibise, Sakyi, & Lund, 2023).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, minimalist painting is a therapeutic remedy to individuals with mental health challenges in Imo state, Nigeria. This study focuses on the application that has provided the

evidence to support the proposition that painting art are therapeutic with psychiatric patients of anxiety and depression, could produce a good benefit in improving non-verbal communication between patients and the on-side medical team, helping with their treatment and enhancing the moods therefore, painting is a meditative act, it takes you out of yourself, freeing yourself from your physical limitations. This means you are only focusing on the present and on the artwork in front of you as you paint, freeing your mind from worries and intrusive thoughts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Students dealing with a lot of stress can reduce their cortisol levels through art therapy and reduce the risk of dying from heart disease. Stress Can Increase risk for Heart Disease. The implications of art therapy are numerous, but to uncover more we should encourage more people to engage with this research. Create whatever you find interesting, and create a lot of it. The more you create, the more your craft will improve and your style will be refined. The strategy is to find things that will inspire and keep the enthusiasm at high levels when applying artwork in painting. If art therapy is not attempted, people may miss out on the opportunities for self-expression and neurological activation that are offered. Other types of therapies, such as verbal-based therapies, that do not involve the creative process may not result in the same outcomes as art therapy. Art therapy is a broad genre that includes many mediums and is adaptable to fit a patient's need. Existing research already shows how art therapy can help treat certain conditions, and there may be correlational evidence that art therapy can indirectly prevent deaths. For example, patients who are diagnosed with depression may be suicidal, and since art therapy improves well-being, it may help to prevent suicides. Also, if someone is feeling suicidal because of poor social relations, art therapy is a great resource to improve relationships and feelings of social acceptance.

Trust yourself. Do not try to paint like your favorite painters, find your own voice. Be your own teacher. Do not just stick with what works or what sells, try new things. A good painter's work is always evolving. Work hard, paint every day, and never give up. You will always have setbacks, and many rejections. You never really "get there." The carrot keeps moving forward. As Kevin Macpherson says, "Painting is sort of like fishing. You are out there enjoying the beautiful day, feeling the wind, taking in the sights and sounds you never really know if you are going to get anything or not.

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